

GIS in Interdisciplinary Research: Colonial Irrigation Policy and Landscape Change In 19th And 20th C. India

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Summary

The increased availability of old maps as geo-referenced layers is an exciting advancement for digital research. This paper highlights GIS as a key method to facilitate interdisciplinary research, especially in environmental history, and aide in effective research dissemination. It also discusses the place of GIS in the humanities and acknowledges critiques of GIS as normative rooted in western and colonial modes of knowledge. Finally, a digital web-mapping out-put is presented integrating old maps and mixed-method research outputs for a non-specialist audience exploring water management in India.

KEYWORDS: cartography, GIS, India, water, web-maps

1. Introduction

Old maps provide a valuable opportunities for environmental research. Digital transformations allow old maps to be studied in new ways beyond ‘close-reading’, through the viewing of geo-referenced layers rather than single physical sheets in an archive (Uhl et al. 2018). There is great potential for interdisciplinary research using digital methods and old maps, however there is a mismatch between disciplines. GIS has been criticised for being ‘reductive’ and ‘normative’ when applied to ‘non-western histories’ (Unangst 2023). There exist misunderstandings from some historians as to the potential of GIS in historical research, and simultaneously a reluctance from GIS specialists to engage with theoretical approaches i.e. postcolonialism. There is a great deal to be learned both approaches, yet it is often difficult to bridge a gap between the two.

This paper aims to demonstrate the strengths of GIS in interdisciplinary research, particularly in bridging these disciplinary divides and providing non-academic outputs. An interactive web-mapping application is presented to demonstrate both the strengths of interdisciplinary approaches, and the ability of GIS as a tool in communication and research dissemination. This paper is contextualised by the research investigating the legacy of colonial irrigation policy on water management in India which draws upon disciplines including geography, environmental history, and political ecology.

2. GIS in the Humanities

GIS was first applied to historical research in the mid 1990s as part of the ‘digital turn’ and now forms its own sub-discipline (Gregory and Ell, 2007). More recently, the application of digital techniques, including GIS, to study the humanities, has grown further in the interdisciplinary field of the digital humanities (DH). DH has its own subfields including the spatial humanities (SH), and environmental humanities (EH). DH is an exciting emerging field of study that champions the potential of interdisciplinary research and digital methods. However, as within the discipline of geography, there remains tension between qualitative and quantitative approaches. This has resulted in ‘qualitative GIS’

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approaches that apply mixed methods to bridge the divide and advocate for collaborative work from both quantitative and qualitative work (Elwood and Cope 2009; Gregory and Geddes 2014; Leszczynski, 2009).

GIS has received criticism for its potential to impose particular views of history, and its requirement for data to be handled in a standardised way (Gregory and Ell, 2007). More specifically, GIS has been challenged for its 'scientific' conceptions of space, rooted in military and colonial histories (Unangst 2023). The idea of alternative conceptions of space have become an interesting area of research, particularly the discussion of pre-colonial indigenous mapping (Murrieta-Flores et al. 2021). Despite this, this paper argues that collections of colonial maps, in combination with GIS methods, can provide significant insights for environmental history despite their challenging histories. Such research requires a careful approach which must be contextualised with a postcolonial view; itself a challenge to engage with especially for scholars without specific humanities background. This often results in these difficult topics being avoided altogether. This paper provides an example of how GIS, when embedded within interdisciplinary research design, contributes to environmental history whilst bridging quantitative and qualitative divides and engaging with postcolonial critiques.

3. Studying Colonial Irrigation Policy in India

3.1. Research Design

To overcome challenges outlined above, GIS methods were combined with archival study and qualitative interviews for a multi-method approach. First, Archival study was undertaken at the British Library and the National Library of Scotland (NLS), investigating the creation of the Survey of India (SOI) maps through accompanying documents and reports. Then, digitised and georeferenced old maps SOI from NLS (see: Fleet 2019) were layered on satellite imagery to investigate spatial patterns in the use of an ancient irrigation technique (irrigation tanks) in South India (Evans et al., 2024). Clusters of wet and dry irrigation tanks were identified using LISA analysis (Anselin, 1995). An interesting wet cluster in Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu was then selected for field investigation, where semi-structured interviews were conducted over a one-month period. This provided detailed insights into the lived experiences of irrigation tank users and an element of ground-truthing.

3.2 Results

First, the archival study focused on SOI cartography during the British colonial period (1858-1947), specifically how and why water was mapped. This was a more traditional 'close reading' of the maps and accompanying documents that provided details on specific survey techniques and cartographic production. Ultimately, this research analysed how cartography played a crucial role in the development of canal networks in Punjab, where the mapping of fluvial environments was first explored by the SOI. Cartography played a significant role in the restructuring of the landscape of Punjab physically, environmentally, and economically.

Then, the combination of geo-spatial analysis, semi-structured interviews and archival research provided multi-scalar, interdisciplinary insights into the environmental history of India. The use of traditional GIS techniques revealed clear spatial patterns of irrigation tanks at a regional scale that were intrinsically connected to the British colonial irrigation policies. This quantitative analysis facilitated the identification of important wet/dry clusters that became the focus of field-based investigation.

Finally, the qualitative interviews focused on the city-scale, analysing one significant cluster of tanks in South-India. The results reveal the emergence of a new era of tank irrigation in urban India, with tank restoration schemes increasing in popularity. The interview data provided a wealth of material exploring the benefits and challenges of such schemes, reflective of broader shifts across India of the move away from tanks as a water resource towards tanks as green/blue urban spaces.

Figure 1: A diagram explaining the research design and relevant data / techniques

Together, the techniques provide a multi-scalar, interdisciplinary analysis of the history of colonial irrigation policies and their impact on the water resources of India today. This approach helps to inform current water management and heritage restoration, as well as deepening understandings of the legacy of India’s colonial past. These three methods worked in tandem to overcome limitations of GIS and quantitative methods providing ‘ground-truths’ as well and situating the research within a postcolonial framing.

3.3 Web-mapping Output

To demonstrate how digital methods and old maps can be combined, an interactive web-map application was created in partnership with NLS (Figures 2a, b). The application, created with OpenLayers, allowed users to interact with a seamless layer of the SOI maps alongside the research results. First, a side-by-side viewer displays satellite imagery alongside old maps with tank ‘wetness’ values across the study area. Users can zoom to explore specific tank features on the maps and satellite imagery. The second tab displays interview data from Coimbatore next to a map of the city, highlighting the irrigation tanks. Users can click a tank, and the text panel will automatically scroll to the interviews conducted at that sight. Photographs have also been included in the left panel to provide a contextual, ground-level detail that cannot be provided in the traditional mapping interface.

Figure 2 A + B: The interactive web-map application produced in partnership with the NLS. A shows irrigation tank 'wetness' values, and B shows the results of qualitative interviews in Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu.

4. Conclusion

This paper has demonstrated an attempt to overcome the criticisms of GIS through an interdisciplinary, multi-method research design. It shows how such approaches can offer new insights on environmental

history that can impact real-world policy, in this case water management in India. Further, it showcases the strengths of interdisciplinary research, and highlights GIS as a tool to aid in interdisciplinary work as well as an excellent method of research dissemination to non-academic audiences. With the ever-increasing availability of old maps as geo-referenced sheet layers, such techniques in the study of interdisciplinary environmental history can continue to bridge the gaps between disciplines and the qualitative – quantitative divide.

Reproducibility Statement

The web application can be accessed [here](#). The associated code is available [here](#).

More information about accessing and using NLS georeferenced maps can be found [here](#)

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Biographies

Charlotte Evans is a post-doctoral research associate at the University of Manchester on the NERC Digital Solutions Programme. She specialises in GIS and interdisciplinary research and is particularly interested in cartography and environmental history.

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